

Cory Harow is an emergency medicine physician affiliated with many hospitals in Florida, including Capital Regional Medical Center, Lakeside Medical Center, Palms West Hospital, Rockford Memorial Hospital, Palm Beach Gardens Medical Center, West Boca Medical Center. Dr. Harow also collaborates with other doctors and specialists without joining any medical groups.

He has over 19 years of diverse experience, mainly in emergency medicine. He is certified in emergency medicine by the American Board of Emergency Medicine. Dr. Harow has his medical licenses for Florida State and Illinois State.

As a philanthropist, Dr. Harow has been contributing and donating to many Israeli charity organizations, including Yashar Lechayal, Standing Together, the Helping Israel Fund and JNF.

He provides his scholarship program for soldiers who cannot afford university tuition, with the help of the Organization Friends of Israel Defense Force.

At the age of 19, he has been serving in the Israel Defense Force.